

CHARACTERISATION OF THE BOTTOM ASH OF THE LAFIA OBI COAL

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ABSTRACT

This investigation characterised the bottom ash of Lafia Obi coal sourced from Lafia, Nassarawa State, Nigeria. The coal sample was heated to a temperature of 950°C in a closed gas kiln to obtain the cream-colour bottom ash as the coal combustion residue which was taken to laboratory for characterisation. The mineralogical composition through X-ray diffraction showed the dominant presence of quartz with other minerals in minor quantities. The elemental oxides analysis through X-ray fluorescence spectrophotometry revealed SiO₂ (52.90%) and Al₂O₃ (28.49%) as major constituent oxides among others. The total percentage of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃ which are the pozzolanic content was 85.04% which ranks the bottom ash high in Class F according to the ASTM bottom ash classification. The LOI (10.20%) is high being above the 6% allowed in many countries. The ultimate analysis results reveal a high carbon content of 60.82%, which places the bottom ash as having high heating value. The low percentage of sulphur (0.01%) and nitrogen (0.5%) presents it as having less potential for releasing harmful pollutants to the environment. The thermogravimetric curve revealed the stability of the material up to a temperature of 250°C. The low onset temperature of 250°C led to a thermal degradation between 250°C and 350°C. The peak temperature was observed to be about 500°C. In conclusion, the Lafia Obi bottom has high heat content. It could also be investigated for partial replacement of cement as a result of its high pozzolanic content. The foregoing will be very economical as bottom ash is far cheaper than cement.

Keywords: Bottom ash, Silica, Heating value, Pozzolanic content

INTRODUCTION

Bottom ash is primarily a non-combustible residue of coal combustion in a power furnace, boiler, plant or incinerator. It is one of the four coal combustion residuals, the other three being fly ash, flu gas desulfurization, and boiler slag (USEPA, 2021). Bottom ash is so named because it is the ash that falls to the bottom of the boiler's combustion chamber called a firebox, whereas the ash portion that escapes up the chimney is called fly ash. Thus bottom ash is heavier than fly ash.

Coal is combustible and is usually black or brownish-black in colour. It is a form of sedimentary rock having a high content of carbon as well as hydrocarbons (EIA, 2023). It contains the energy stored by plants that existed for a long time in swampy forests. The plants were covered by layers of rock and dirt for so many years. The pressure and heat that resulted converted the plants into what is called coal today (Omidiji, 2017). Like some other African countries, Nigeria is blessed with coal-rich locations, including Enugu, Kogi, Benue, Kwara, Abia, Delta, Edo, Bauchi, Imo, Adamawa, and Nassarawa States. Coal was discovered in Nigeria in 1909 at Udi Ridge in Enugu State, as a result of which coal mining operations started in 1916 at Ogbete Mine in Enugu. Ogbete Mine started operation with the mining of 25,511 metric tons of coal. This figure continued

to increase to the extent that at a point Enugu mined 790,030 tons of coal before 1967, after which there was mining decline resulting from the emergence of civil war in Nigeria. During the Civil War (1967 to 1970), a mine was located as Okaba Coal Mine in the present Kogi State. These mines were later merged into Nigerian Coal Corporation (NCC).

Compared to oil and gas, coal is the most demanded fossil fuel as a result of its abundance and cheapness globally (Jamaludin, 2009). The global adoption and usage of coal leads to the production of huge amounts of waste, including bottom ash disposed as landfill. Researchers usually get samples of bottom ash disposed from ash ponds and analyse them to ensure compliance with local environmental impact standards (Mandala and Sinha, 2014).

Coal bottom ash is now mainly used in road construction and concrete block production. It is also used in construction of road bases, sub bases, structural fills, and asphaltic concrete aggregate (Singh, 2024). It has been investigated for optimisation as a replacement for fine aggregate in concrete production and is being investigated as an additive in refractory coating production (Kannan and Kumar, 2017). Compared to sand, bottom ash is weaker, lighter, and more brittle. The sources and environment of bottom ash production determines its content, quality and uses (CEWEP, 2024). Besides, the physical properties of

bottom ash also depend on the properties of rock detritus contained in the fissures of the coal seams. Variation in the rock detritus on source basis results in diversity of coal bottom ash. Its contents determine its impacts on the environment. The engineering utilization of bottom ash is a potential solution for its disposal, but its environmental impact needs to be studied. Thus, there are diverse varieties of bottom ash, and individual characterisations are important in an attempt to decide their best applications and environmental impacts (Backreedy *et al.*, 2003; Bauxer, 2005), hence this Lafia Obi coal bottom ash characterisation.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Material Collection

The coal from which the bottom ash was obtained was sourced from Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The coal is so named Lafia Obi coal.

Bottom Ash Production

The coal sample was heated to a temperature of 950°C in a closed gas kiln. The combustion of the coal led to the production of cream-colour bottom ash as the coal combustion residue.

Mineralogical and Chemical Composition of the Bottom Ash

The mineralogical composition of the Lafia Obi coal bottom ash was investigated with the aid of X-Ray Diffractometer (XRD) as powdered samples were pelletized before being sieved to 0.07 mm. The sieved samples were then taken in an aluminum alloy grid (35 mm x 50 mm) on a flat glass plate and covered with paper. The samples were gently pressed with a hand in a glove in an attempt to get them compacted. The sample was run through the Rigaku D/Max-IIIC X-ray diffractometer.

The chemical composition of a sample of the bottom ash was also investigated through X-ray fluorescence spectrophotometry.

Thermal Analysis

The Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) instrument measures the change in weight with respect to temperature. The dynamic properties that can be determined through TGA include thermal stability of materials, oxidation stability, estimated lifetime, decomposition kinetics, moisture content, and volatile content. The aluminium pan was filled with 10 - 15mg of the prepared sample. The sample was thereafter heated from the ambient temperature up to 600°C, at the heating rate of 10°C/min. The resulting weight loss was recorded accordingly.

Ultimate Analysis

The ultimate analysis was carried out to determine the presence and quantity of elemental carbon, hydrogen,

nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur contained by the bottom ash. During the ultimate analysis, 2 g of oil sample was weighed into platinum crucible and placed in a leibig-pregle chamber, which contained magnesium percolate and sodium hydroxide according to ASTM 3174-76. The sample produced carbon dioxide and water when burned off. The water was absorbed by magnesium percolate, while CO₂ was absorbed by sodium hydroxide. The amounts of water and carbon dioxide were calculated by difference.

An elemental analyser (LECO CHN 2000) was used in the elemental determination of hydrogen, carbon, and nitrogen. Oxygen was determined by difference. The amount of carbon residue was determined based on ASTM D 189. The heating value was determined by calorimetry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mineralogical and Chemical Compositions Results

The mineralogical composition of the Lafia Obi coal bottom ash was revealed through X-ray diffraction, which shows twenty peaks as shown in Figure 1. The peaks showed the dominant presence of quartz. Other minerals identified were mica, iron oxide, calcium oxide, kaolin, and zeolite.

The results of the elemental oxides analysis of the bottom ash carried out through X-ray fluorescence (XRF) are presented in Table 1. The result shows that silicon in its oxide form (SiO₂) is observed to occur as the major element in the sample (52.90%), followed by aluminum in its oxide form (Al₂O₃) with 28.49%, while Fe, Ti, Ca, Mg, and Na occurred as minor elements in their oxide forms. The result agrees with literature which reveals the major composition of bottom ash as silica (SiO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃), and ferric oxide (Fe₂O₃) as well as calcium oxide (CaO) and small percentages of other oxides like K₂O, TiO₂, MgO, Na₂O, CO₂, MnO, P₂O₅ and Loss on Ignition (LOI). The total percentage composition of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ is 85.04% which falls within the range of 70 - 93% bottom ash categorised by American Standard for Testing and Materials (ASTM) C618 as class F (Sadon *et al.*, 2017).

The value of loss on ignition obtained for Lafia Obi coal bottom ash as 10.20% is worthy of consideration. The allowable value of LOI varies from one country to another. The limitation on LOI is to ensure that less harm is done to the environment. For example, the maximum LOI allowed in many countries is 6% (Sadon *et al.*, 2017). Obviously, the LOI of Lafia Obi coal bottom ash is above the allowable limit by ASTM. For concrete application, high value of LOI will negatively affect the development of the concrete strength (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2023). Variability of coal ash sources, processing and ignition temperatures impact the results of LOI (Lymn *et al.*, 2017).

The metallic elements present were Ba, Cu, Cr, Ni and Zn (Figure 1). The presence of heavy metals such as Zinc,

Chromium and Nickel can be harmful to the environment (Abdullah *et al.*, 2019).

Results of the Ultimate Analysis

The ultimate analysis of bottom ash significantly determines its utilisation. Table 2 shows the results of the ultimate analysis carried out on the bottom ash sample.

the higher its calorific value (Abubakar andBaharudin, 2012).

Thermal Analysis

The thermogravimetric (TG) curve for the Lafia Obi coal is presented in Figure 2. The material was stable at a temperature less than 250°C as no significant weight loss was observed. The thermal degradation occurs between

Figure 1: XRD Result of the Lafia Obi Coal.

Table 1: Chemical Compositions of the Lafia Obi Coal in Percentage

SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	CaO	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	MnO	MgO	Na ₂ O	LOI	Ba	Cu	Cr	Ni	Zn
52.90	28.49	3.65	1.18	1.90	-	0.99	-	0.08	0.05	10.20	662.61	28.33	100.30	31.60	210.45

Table 2: Data from Ultimate Analysis of the Lafia Obi coal Bottom Ash

C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	O (%)	S (%)
60.82±0.03	4.02±0.02	0.5±0.02	33.05±0.06	0.01±0.3

The results show that Lafia Obi coal bottom ash has elemental carbon of 60.82%. The high carbon content is an indication of its high heating value. However, while employing bottom ash in concrete making, the high carbon content can deprive water, and thus bring about increase in water demand (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2023). The sulphur content is 0.01% which is significantly low. Low sulphur content shows low potential for release of harmful gases associated with the presence of sulfur to the environment. The content of nitrogen, 0.5%, is not so high, signifying low potential for generation of pollutants such as nitrogen oxides. Its oxygen content is 33.05%. The oxygen content is essential for bottom ash ranking, as the lower the oxygen content, the higher the calorific value, which implies the degree of heat content of the bottom ash. The hydrogen content is 4.02%. The higher the hydrogen contents of bottom ash,

250°C and about 350°C at which there is sudden steep fall in weight. The onset temperature marks the beginning of degradation. The low onset temperature (250°C) must have been due to the high volatile contents which are easily released at a low temperature. At the peak temperature, nearly all the volatile content must have been removed. The peak temperature is observed to be about 500°C.

CONCLUSION

The characteristics of the Lafia Obi coal bottom ash have been investigated. The mineralogical and chemical composition revealed that silicon oxide and aluminum oxide are predominant compounds in the bottom ash sample with other oxides in minor quantities. Of significance is the total percentage composition of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ being 85.04%, which makes it a high-ranking bottom ash belonging to Class F according ASTM. The foregoing implies that the bottom ash has high pozzolanic contents and can be investigated for partial replacement of cement. The elemental carbon composition is high suggesting high heating value of the bottom ash but tendency to consume more water when used as a fine

aggregate in concrete. The low content of sulphur and nitrogen suggests that less quantity of hazardous gases is associated with it and is therefore fairly environmental friendly. On the other hand, the high percentage of LOI being above the allowed percentage in most countries for environmental safety is of concern. In conclusion, the Lafia Obi coal bottom ash has a high caloric value. It also has a high pozzolanic value, and thus can be investigated for partial replacement of cement.

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Figure 2: The Thermogravimetric Analysis Curve for Lafia Obi Coal

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